

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Distribution and status of West African manatee (*Trichechus senegalensis*) in Niger

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Article published on January 26, 2017

Key words: Manatee, Distribution, Legislation, Conservation, Niger

Abstract

This study aims to improve knowledge on the distribution and status of West African manatee (*Trichechus senegalensis*) in Niger in order to identify the main threats facing the manatee in its distribution area and to promote its sustainable management. It was carried out on the Nigerien portion of the Niger river from its entry into the territory from Koutougou (department of Ayorou) on its exit in Dolé (department of Gaya). The method consisted of socio-economic surveys and identification of feeding indices. The abundance of feeding signs and manatee parts (bones, skin, smoked meat, etc) showed that presence of the species. This study revealed the existence legal texts which confer to the manatee integral protection in Niger and this in disfavor of the local population who could no longer fish. However, human threats coupled with the effects of climate change are the greatest challenges to the conservation of the species. This study showed that manatee occupies an emblematic place in the traditions of the populations which could contribute in the elaboration of efficient conservation strategy for the survival of the manatee.

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Introduction

The West African Manatee (*Trichechus senegalensis*) is a large aquatic mammal found in coastal and inland wetlands of Western Africa between Mauritania and Angola, and inland as far as Mali, Niger and Chad. It occurs in coastal and estuarine habitats, coastal lagoons and the lower reaches of most river systems from the Senegal River of Mauritania/Senegal to the Longa River in Angola. (UNEP/CMS, 2008; Todman *et al.*, 2008). It is classified on the red list of the IUCN and the annex I of the Convention on Illegal Trade of Endangered Species of wildlife and Fauna (CITES, 2016). The manatee is a well known animal species in Niger because in 1901 already, Gratiolet mentioned its presence around Sinder, a village upstream on the river Niger. The researches made by Ciofolo and Sadou (1996) enabled to demonstrate the presence of manatee throughout the river Niger from Yassane a village close to the border with Mali up to Dolé, a village on the border with the Federal republic of Nigeria. In Niger, the law n°62-28 of 04 august 1962 placed the manatee in the annex 1 of animal species which benefit from total protection. This law was reinforced by the law n°98-07 of 29 avril 1998 regulating hunting and Fauna protection in Niger. Notwithstanding this classification which had given to the species a special status, habitat lost, climate change and human activities, mainly poaching manatee for its meat and its various usages in the traditional medicine, dam's constructions and rice cultivation are the main challenges facing the species' survival. The objective of this reflection is to improve knowledge on the dynamics and status of the manatee in Niger for its sustainable management. This includes assessing the perception of local communities about the dynamics and status of the manatee.

Materials and methods

Study area

The study area is constituted by the portion of the Niger River in Niger republic, the largest river in West Africa. It originates in the Fouta Djallon mounts in Guinea and crosses successively Mali, Niger, Benin and Nigeria. It traverses the Niger territory on about 550 km from Ayorou (region of Tillabéry) to Gaya (Region of Dosso) (Fig. 1).

The population of the area is estimated at 5,977,951 inhabitants in 2014 with a population density ranging from 13.6 persons/km² in Ouallam to 35.6 persons/km² in Kollo (INS, 2014). The main activity, namely agriculture, is characterized by a great diversity of speculation traditionally based on family-type production systems. Rice growing, market, gardening and arboriculture are also practiced along the river. Artisanal fishing is practiced, while livestock raising concerns the majority of households. Most of the fodder comes from the residues of the rice fields and the production of bourgou (*Echinochloa stagnina*), much appreciated by livestock.

Materials

This study necessitated the elaboration a data collection sheet to conduct a socio-economic survey of the local populations in relation to the distribution of the manatee. Interviews included (i) the presence of the manatee, (ii) the abundance and distribution of the manatee, (iii) the types of vegetation in the river, (iv) the physical characteristics of the river, Perception of populations on the manatee, etc. Field investigations required a motorized canoe equipped with a 45 hp motor, a Garmin 60 GPS, a digital camera, portable sonar and a Secchi disc. Desk review provided an overview of the work on the manatee and a reconnaissance mission in the villages of the study area.

Methods

Sampling

Sampling is based on the results and information gathered in a preliminary investigation. The sites were selected on the basis of three criteria: (i) indices of presence of the manatee (bones, pieces of skin, signs of feeding, etc.), (ii) high numbers of fishermen in the village, and) Presence of a water master. Thus, of the fifty fishing villages and camps along the river, from Koutougou in the department of Ayérou to Boumba in the department of Falmey, twenty-eight were selected. The selected sites represent 54% of the sampling rate and satisfy the criteria of the Pareto law (Elbekkage, 1993) which stipulates that for a sample to be sufficiently representative, the sampling rate should be between 15 and 20%. In these villages, four groups of actors were interviewed:

fishermen, women, young people and water masters. In each group, 10 subjects were interviewed; hence 1120 people were covered by the survey.

Data collection

One of the biggest obstacles to finding a manatee is the difficulty of seeing it on the surface of the water. It is a major handicap in measuring the dynamics of its population. Indirect indices and interviews remain the most preferred methods for estimating its population. These techniques have been widely used for the census of the manatee population in Florida and Belize (Bengtson & Magor, 1979), the Dominican Republic (Belitsky & Belitsky, 1980), Haiti (Rathbun *et al.*, 1985) Honduras (Rathbun *et al.*, 1983), Puerto Rico (Powell *et al.*, 1981, O’Shea *et al.*, 1986). Interviews were also used for the manatee by Nishiwaki *et al.* (1984), Sierra Leone (Grigione, 1989), Cameroon (Powell, 1996), and Niger (Ciofolo & Sadou, 1982) and Roth & Waitkuwait, 1996). In the course of this study, several methodological tools were used. This includes a review of the literature on the state of knowledge of previous studies and studies related to this study and questionnaires related respectively to the habitat of the manatee, its diet, Socio-economic aspects and its values. Before the survey phase, we conducted a reconnaissance mission in the villages of the study area.

Data analysis

The data was collected and Excel spread sheet was

used for data processing and graphs, while Arc GIS 10.1 facilitated the production of the maps.

Results

Age class of the interviewees

The local populations living on the Niger River rely on products derived from their main activities, namely fishing and agriculture. Table 1 shows that the age group between 36 and 60 is the largest component of the population engaged in fishing. As for the age groups between 18 and 35, 61 to 70 and more, we note a small number (Table 1).

Table 1. Classe d’âge des personnes interviewees.

Classe d’âge (ans)	Nombre de pêcheurs	Fréquence (%)
18-25	33	2,9
26-30	58	5,2
31-35	43	3,8
36-40	89	7,9
41-45	112	10,0
46-50	175	15,6
51-55	182	16,3
56-60	195	17,4
61-65	123	11,0
65-70	87	7,8
70	23	2,1
Total	1120	100,0

Manatee observation

Most of the persons interviewed (about 68%) reported observing at least one individual while out on the river, while about 32% said they had never observed a manatee on the river (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Study area. (Niger river in Niger republic)

Manatee abundance

The Table 2 shows that 79% of the people interviewed say that the manatees are more numerous nowadays while 5% did not provide a response.

Table 2. Abondance du lamantin dans le fleuve.

Oui	Non	Ne sais pas	Total
79%	16%	5%	100%

Human activities

Human activities largely rhythm the life on the River Niger. Fishing occupies a predominant place in the daily life of the population and represents 58.28% of the population while agriculture occupies 36.2% and various pollutions 5.52% (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Manatee's observation frequency.

Manatee capture

Since the dawn of time, the capture of the manatee is a great privilege and gives the fisherman a certain respect and reputation among the populations. However, only 21.83% of those interviewed claim to have caught at least one manatee in their life. 65.26% of the interviewees said they had never caught a manatee, while 12.92% were reluctant to provide answers to the question asked (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Ideal moment manatee observation.

Ideal periods for manatees' observation

According to about 80% of the interviewees, the period of the local flood (June) known as "red waters" is the most favorable for observation of the manatee (Fig 4). 17.3% of those interviewed say they encounter the manatee during the Guinean flood (December), when the river is full of water and the food is abundant. 3.34% of people say that the manatee can be observed during the low water period when the water level decreases, which often turns the river into a string of giant ponds.

Fig. 4. Manatee's capture.

Consumption of manatee's meat

Meat from aquatic wildlife is a dietary supplement that contributes to the food balance of populations and a source of income.

In fact, manatee meat is highly valued by local populations and this is proved by the fact that about 46% of people claim to have consumed manatee meat at least once in their lives (Fig. 6). While 37.6% said they had never eaten manatee meat and 16.7% abstained to give any answer.

Fig. 5. Ideal period for manatee observation.

Fig. 6. Main human activities.

Fig. 7. Manatee's meat consumption.

Discussion

Age class for the interviewees

The local populations living on river Niger banks live mainly on products derived from their activities, namely fishing and agriculture. Fishing occupies an important place in their daily life since it provides the nutritional supplement rich in animal protein and ensures the procurement of monetary income. Fishing occupies a large part of the labor force and the Table 1 shows that the age range between 36 and 60 is the largest component of the population which is concerned. As for the age groups between 18 and 30, 61 to 70 and more, we notice a smaller number. This is due to two key factors: the 18-30 group includes young people who are currently engaged in their studies and other more lucrative activities because they see fishing as an activity that is no longer profitable and much more risky. As for the 61-70 and over, they consider that they are old enough and tired for this activity.

They prefer to transmit their knowledge to future generations. Observations of manatees by fishermen can take place throughout the day: morning, full day, evening, night.

However, they are easier during the dry season. Indeed, during the rainy season, the water level is higher and these animals can feed on the different plants' roots under water, whereas in the dry season they have to climb partly on the river bank to feed. It is then a privileged moment to observe them. Their presence may also be indicated by the remains of the plants from which they have been feeding which float on the surface of the water. Manatees are usually seen alone. Nevertheless, observations of female with a young, couples and groups have been reported. The manatees flee from the human presence, probably because of the hunting pressure they are subjected to. Although recognized as harmless, they can capsize a canoe with the waves they produce during a precipitate flight.

Manatees' observation frequency

The manatee is an emblematic animal species in Niger and is well rooted in the customs of local populations. The local population of the study area demonstrates good knowledge of wildlife. According to fishermen, solitary individuals would generally be adult males or gestating females. As for the group of individuals observed, it is generally a female in periods of heat that is pursued by a group of males. During the breeding season, fishermen claim that a group of males chase a female. Mating occurs at the surface of the water and at any time of the day or night. The males are grouped around a female in heat; it is the stronger that manages to mate. During the mating period, a female can be pursued by about twenty males.

Table 1 shows that the manatee is present in the Niger River. Indeed, about 72% of those interviewed claim to have met at least one manatee on their river outings. The reluctance of people to provide answers about 31% of the questionnaires demonstrates the severity of the legislation on the protection of wildlife in Niger. According to the village chief of Kareykopto, fishermen prefer to bury the remains of the manatee than to show them to the wildlife protection agents. The observations of manatees by the fishermen can take place throughout the day: morning, full day, evening or in the night.

However, they are easier during the dry season. Indeed, during the rainy season, the water level is higher and these animals can feed on the different roots of plants under water, whereas in the dry season they have to climb in part on the vegetation to feed. It is then a privileged moment to observe them.

The relative abundance of the manatee in this area is due to the nature of the river, in particular the presence of a very deep bed in which rich vegetation and a dense fish population develop. These results are confirmed by the work of Awaiss & Saadou (1998) that the amphibian hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibius*), the West African manatee (*Trichechus senegalensis*) and the spotted otter (*Lutra maculicollis*) are of sedentary mammals linked to Niger aquatic ecosystems. They are observed in the River Niger, particularly at the level of the spraying zones rich in *Echinochloa stagnina* (Bourgou) and in the tributaries for the manatee. These results also corroborate those obtained during the socio-economic survey (ECOPAS, 2006), which show that the existing bathymetric conditions are very favorable to the aquatic fauna shelter (hippopotamus, crocodiles, manatees, fish, Turtles) during low water.

Manatees' abundance

The Table 2 shows that 79% of those interviewed say that manatees are more numerous today, while 5% have not responded. The reluctance of the population to pronounce on the abundance of the manatee is due to the severity of the legislation on the protection of wildlife in Niger and the heavy penalties associated to the crimes. This is probably due to the strengthening of the law on wildlife protection and the punishment of offenders. In contrast, 16% report that the manatee population is in marked decline due to several factors:

- Silting up of the river.
- Human activities: fishing, irrigation, canoe engine noise, pirogue motor oil.
- Breeding cycle of the species.
- Illegal fishing because of meat and traditional medicine.

- Migration of the animal to the deepest and quietest areas.
- Habitat loss.

Ideal moment for manatee observation

According to Akoi (2004), the activities of the manatee (feeding, reproduction, displacement) are largely impacted by human presence. Manatees flee from places where fishermen throw their nets or place their traps. Manatees are naturally exposed to contact with humans, because their main habitats are productive wetland ecosystems. According to Nathalie Bréheret (2007), observations of manatees by fishermen can take place throughout the day: morning, full day, evening, night. However, they are easier during the dry season. Indeed, during the rainy season, the water level is higher and these animals can feed on the different roots of plants under water, whereas in the dry season, they must lift themselves partly on the bank to feed at the bourgoutieres. According to 79.2% of the persons interviewed, the period of the local flood known as "red water" (June) is the most conducive period for manatee observation. This red flood occurs at the beginning of the rainy season, which corresponds to the reproduction period of the manatee (Fig. 4). 17.3% of those interviewed say they encounter the manatee during the Guinean flood (December) when the river is filled with water and the food is abundant. 3.34% of people say that the manatee can be observed during the low water period when the water level decreases, which often turns the river into a string of giant ponds.

Human activities

Manatees are reputed to have no natural predators. Crocodiles, which could attack them, have indeed become rare in the river (Kandadji, 2006). The threats to this species would come mainly from habitat alteration, which is the direct result of certain management policies such as the construction of dams and hydro-agricultural developments. To this should be added the illegal hunting and the destruction of the habitat by the climatic changes. In addition the increase of the population along the rivers of manatees has a direct impact on the distribution of the species.

Fig. 5 shows that fishing accounts for about 58% of the activities conducted in the study area. This indicates the pressure exerted by these activities on the manatee. These activities which occupy all the age groups from 18 to 70 years, is now decreasing with the disappearance of pageants customs and the Islamization of populations. In fact, the capture and consumption of the meat of the manatee is a cult that is nowadays considered as pageant. The sorkhos affirm that "the manatees have jinns and before catching them, we must implore the jinns". The ceremony is preceded by a ritual that requires the sacrifice of a chicken, the incantation of verses. The fisherman must be inducted with oil mixed with a powder of herbs and trees' barks. He must wear amulets and must spend 2 or 3 days without performing any religious acts. There is unanimity that the authorization of the hunting of the manatee, will return to their old traditions.

Before hunting the manatee, the sorkho must sacrifice a white chicken to hunt jinns. The blood of the chicken is poured into the river, the meat is cut into pieces and distributed to the children. The elders prepare a millet soup with sugar, and they pour some of it into the river and give the rest to the children. After this sacrifice, one must collect the traditional plants, leaves or the bark of certain trees. A powder is put into the water, and the fishermen bath themselves with it. Then they can go on the water and the manatee will appear before them to be killed.

Manatee capture

According to NDOUR (2010) all time, throughout the world, the manatee was killed for its flesh first, then for its therapeutic and aphrodisiac attributes. Illegal fishing is considered as the main threat that has accentuated the decline of manatee populations. Such acts are still to be deplored because poaching still persists in places. Due to its large size, the capture of a manatee is very popular with local fishermen. Its meat is generally considered delicious, while many other parts of the animal are used for consumption and traditional medicine (Moussa, 2012). Widespread beliefs are also associated with most parts of his body.

Even when carried out on a small scale, hunting is a real threat to the animal given its low reproduction rate (birth of a calf every two or three years). Capture of the manatee is an event and an occasion for rejoicing in the village. Indeed, a fisherman who has captured a manatee is elevated to the rank of brave and is a pride for his family. We must not, however, be tempted to accuse these local populations for their uses of natural resources and for their defense of resources against predators (Chardonnet *et al.*, 1995). This prohibition of access to resources was considered by the village communities as an exaction, alienation or spoliation of their natural rights which he considered as a divine gift. Human impacts on protected areas and their surroundings are the result of high population growth coupled with population poverty (Amougou, 2000).

Fig. 3 shows that about 22% of interviewees confirmed that they caught the manatee while about 65% said they did. The additional information gathered allowed us to say that 12.92% who are reluctant to provide answers to the question asked would be due to the legislation in favor of the protection of the species. Indeed, in Niger, the manatee is classified in the list 1 of the mammals fully protected by the law n° 98-07 of April 29th, 1998 fixing the Regime of the Hunting and the Protection of the Fauna. This classification gives the species a special legal status which contributes to its protection. Indeed, according to Article 43 of this law: anyone who has hunted animals fully protected outside the legal provisions will be punished with imprisonment from 2 months to 6 years and a fine from 40 000 to 4 000 000 FCFA, Or one of these two penalties only. Despite the full protection of the manatee and the penalties incurred by delinquents, it is now threatened by illegal fishing.

Manatee meat consumption

An active trade of the West African manatee, including meat, oil and parts of the body, used for traditional pharmacopoeia, among others. trade occurs mainly at the local or national level. While some countries need better national legislation and policies to stem this trade,

most countries have appropriate legislation in place but are struggling to implement them. Enforcement of the Wildlife Trade Act is costly because it requires patrols and surveys in rural areas, whereas a very strict approach does not always work well of ten, legislation that is beneficial to wildlife and natural resources is weaker than other government policies (Powell, 1996; Reeves *et al.*, 1988). In Niger, manatees are still hunted fairly regularly for meat, although they are not actively searched and captured on fishing trips.

The Fig. 6 shows that 45.7% of people interviewed consumed at least manatee meat once in their lifetime while 37.6% claimed that they never. 16.7% of interviewees were reluctant to provide answers to the questions. Further in-depth interviews indicated that populations were reluctant to provide information because of wildlife legislation.

According to the persons surveyed, in the past there were many manatees in the river, at that time hunting was not prohibited, they could kill 3 to 4 per day and in broad daylight without anyone saying anything or do anything. Meanwhile, hunting has made manatee very rare to see, and a law that prohibits hunting is elaborated. However, nowadays only the village notables, former fishermen and the informants of the wildlife services can confirm having consumed the manatee meat. This is due to the fact that they are not afraid of any sanctions or fines from the wildlife services in charge of the implementation of law n°98-07 of April 29th, 1998 fixing the hunting and protection of the wildlife. The preparation of the meat of the manatee requires incantations. These steps are required in the preparations of meat in fear that the consumption of this meat does not harm anyone or make them sick. Before sharing the meat, a part is reserved for the village head, the person who initiated the fisherman and the fisherman who killed the animal. Then the rest is shared among all the members of the village.

The meat is eaten directly while the fat oil is used in cooking food or for oil lamps. The other parts are generally used in the treatment of diseases such as rheumatism,

infertility or sexual impotence and black magic. According to the sorkhos, manatee killing is done by harpoon and the meat called mama alforma (popular meat) is much appreciated and is shared among the villagers. According testimonies collected, the flesh of the manatee would be very nourishing, and possess therapeutic virtues. The sorkhos claim that in the 1980s the price per kilo of manatee meat varied between 200 and 300 FCFA but currently the kilo is sold between 3,000 and 4,500 FCFA and the price varies according to the locality and requirements of the seller. The oil from the fat of the animal is used in feeding, treating rheumatism and feeding oil lamps. According to the sorkhos, an adult manatee can produce up to 5 liters of oil. The economic interest of the manatee is so important that an adult male manatee could be exchanged in Nigeria with a 10-meter boat with an engine (estimated value 2,000,000 FCFA).

- Skin portion 1 cm long: 500 CFA
- Portion of male sex: (0.25 cm) at 10,000 FCFA
- Portion of bone at 4,500 FCFA
- Full male genital apparatus 50,000 CFA (ECOPAS, 2002)

Conclusion

This study carried out between June 2013 and September 2015 on the Niger River provided information on the manatee's status. The socio-economic study revealed that the human population has a good knowledge of aquatic fauna in general and of the manatee in particular. From this study, it appears that there were a conflict between fishermen and the wildlife administration, which protects the manatee by arresting and confiscating fishing gears and Offenders. The strengthening of the legislation and the complains from the fishermen indicate that they have never been given the reasons for this restriction on hunting the manatee. The study revealed that the manatee provides a dietary supplement and a source of income for the populations. The protection of the species upsets the local population because the elders seem worried not to be able to transmit their customs to the younger ones, who do not seem to be concerned by these traditions because of their level of education.

To ensure the long-term success of manatee management, it is essential that communities along the river should be integrated into the design and implementation of conservation programs and to give them a sense of responsibility and ecological values. An education program must reach the main users of the river system in order to contribute to the survival of the species. Ecological monitoring, or even restoration, of wetlands could maintain suitable habitat for the manatee.

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